

“Report on In-Depth Monitoring”

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History of Changes:

Date	Comments	Version
7 June 2024	<i>Initial draft by partners responsible</i>	V0.1
13 June 2024	<i>draft based on feedback from project partners</i>	V0.2
20 June 2024	<i>draft based on feedback from Steering Committee</i>	V0.3
26 June 2024	<i>final version submitted to Participant Portal</i>	V1.0

3 November 2024	<i>draft M27 by partners responsible</i>	V1.1
13 November 2024	<i>draft M27 based on feedback by partners</i>	V1.2
19 November 2024	<i>draft M27 based on feedback by Steering Committee</i>	V1.3
29 November 2024	<i>final version M27 submitted to Participant Portal</i>	V2.0
6 February 2025	<i>draft M30 by partners responsible</i>	V2.1
17 February 2025	<i>draft M30 based on feedback by partners</i>	V2.2
27 February 2025	<i>draft M30 based on feedback by Steering Committee</i>	V2.3
28 February 2025	<i>final version M30 submitted to Participant Portal</i>	V3.0

SUMMARY OF THE PROJECT

INDUSAC's main objective is to develop and validate a state-of-the-art, Industry-Academia collaboration (IAC) mechanism for quick, challenge-driven, human-centred co-creation. It aims to build upon pre-existing IAC mechanisms such as EIT KICs and to facilitate a simple, user-friendly co-creation process that allows to develop solutions that clearly address the needs and interests of companies, students, and researchers in the EU, with special attention to widening and associated countries. Of a highly digitalised nature, our project pilots the mechanism's two main components: a methodology developed by applying human-centred design principles and an online platform aimed at connecting stakeholders from the industry-academia ecosystem and at supporting them throughout their co-creation journey.

The INDUSAC methodology provides the guidance and tools needed to power the process, whilst the platform stands as a networking space for stakeholders to connect, as well as a co-creation arena to develop joint solutions. Through the experience of supporting at least 300 transnational co-creation teams throughout the project lifetime, the INDUSAC mechanism and its two key components will be successively improved until the project ends, delivering a tested mechanism ready for replication and upskilling. It is expected for INDUSAC to also create a dynamic community of industry-academia stakeholders, including at least 1.000 companies, 3.000 students and 300 researchers by project end. The INDUSAC counts with a strong interdisciplinary, cross-sectorial and geographically balanced partnership that counts with the needed expertise and network to achieve our project's goals.

ABSTRACT

INDUSAC project is supporting 300 co-creation projects. Each co-creation team (3-6 student and research members) is solving a challenge of a particular company within 4-8 weeks. The Mentoring Committee oversaw carrying out a quick monitoring of the selected projects to facilitate the co-creation process and to identify any potential improvements needed for the methodology, including the platform. This is the final version of the D3.4 Report on in-depth monitoring. It incorporates the key findings and suggestions from all monitored projects. The Mentoring Committee checked on the progress of the co-creation projects from different rounds and verified whether they were being carried out as specified in the INDUSAC Call for Companies and the INDUSAC Call for Students and Researchers and agreed between the company and the co-creation team. The Mentoring Committee also checked and advised on elements such as clarity of guidelines, adherence to deadlines, timely delivery of results, and communication between the company and the co-creation team. The Mentoring Committee followed the To-Do lists for co-creation teams, corresponding to individual PCA types of the Challenges, that lead the teams through the process of co-creation and helped the Mentoring Committee check the status of a specific activity and insert potential comments / record the progression of major milestones and any problems that may occur over the co-creation project period. Each co-creation project was closely monitored by two members of the mentoring committee. For each monitored project, the Mentoring Committee completed a separate Monitoring Form. In the monitoring process within the first round, the Mentoring Committee selected all 13 projects that started within the framework of INDUSAC, except for three whose completion was expected in mid-June 2024. Within the second round (cut-off for submitting motivation letters on 18 June 2024), the Mentoring Committee selected 7 projects that were completed in the end of September 2024. Finally, as a part of the third round (cut-off for submitting motivation letters on 30 October 2024 and 30 November 2024), the Mentoring Committee selected 10 projects that were completed mainly in January 2025. Based on the feedback provided by the co-creation teams and the companies, and the observations of the Mentoring Committee, improvements of the INDUSAC processes, methodology, and the platform were suggested to increase the effectiveness of co-creation teams, maximise the team members' involvement, and increase the success of the collaborations. The Mentoring Committee altogether monitored 30 co-creation projects. The final version of the D3.4 Report on in-depth monitoring was submitted in February 2025 (M30).

LIST OF ACRONYMS

BAX	Bax Innovation Consulting SL
BIC	Bydgoszcz Industrial Cluster Tool Valley
CCIPB	Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Pécs-Baranya
CIT UPC	UPC Technology Center
CUT	Cyprus University of Technology
EIT	EIT Manufacturing East
EU	European Union
FM	Final Meeting
INDUSAC	Quick Challenge-driven, Human-centred Co-Creation mechanism for INDUSty-Academia Collaborations
INNO	Innoget / INNOVAWIN 2006 SL
JSI	Jožef Stefan Institute
KIT	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
KO	Kick-off Meeting
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M	Month
T	Task
WP	Work Package
PCA	Pre-defined Collaboration Approach

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I. INTRODUCTION

In the first round of the INDUSAC Call for Students and Researchers, 13 co-creation projects were able to start developing the solution following positive reviews of motivation letters by companies submitted by co-creation teams (Spreitzer and Pazaurek 2024a). In the second (Spreitzer and Pazaurek 2024b) and third round of Mentoring Committee work (this report), 7 and 10 co-creation projects were monitored by two members of the mentoring committee, respectively. The same procedure was used for all three rounds.

The Mentoring Committee established contacts with the companies and the co-creation teams. Each co-creation project was closely monitored by two members of the Mentoring Committee. The Mentoring Committee checked on the progress and verified that the co-creation projects were being carried out as specified in the INDUSAC Call for Companies and INDUSAC Call for Students and Researchers and agreed between the company and the co-creation team. Furthermore, the Committee also checked and advised on elements such as clarity of INDUSAC guidelines, adherence to deadlines, timely delivery of results, and communication between the company and the co-creation team. Following the completion of co-creation projects, the Mentoring Committee prepared this deliverable - D3.4 Report on In-Depth Monitoring. The Mentoring Committee members communicated with each other via emails, especially during the implementation of the co-creation projects. During the monitoring process, several meetings of the Mentoring Committee members were organised.

II. THE MENTORING COMMITTEE AND DESCRIPTION OF WORK

The Mentoring Committee with the following members was established for monitoring purposes:

JSI: Matjaž Spreitzer

BAX: Harry Dobbs, Maarten Buysse

CIT UPC: Radivoj Malić

CCIPB: Szabina Pazaurek

CUT: Eliza Nikolaou (first and second round), Sara Mariza Vryonides (third round)

Description of work:

The Mentoring Committee members organised video conference meetings or e-mail communication with the teams and the companies. The Mentoring Committee members followed the To-Do lists that co-creation teams also received as an optional guideline at the beginning of their work. Each co-creation project was closely monitored by two members of the Mentoring Committee. While companies dictate the main progression of the co-creation project, the To-Do lists, corresponding to PCA types of Challenges, help lead the teams through the process of co-creation. The Mentoring Committee members regularly check the status of a specific co-creation case and insert potential comments, record the progression, any problems, troubleshooting etc., in the Monitoring Form (Annex 1). Based on the feedback provided by the co-creation teams and the companies, and their own observations, the Mentoring Committee provides suggestions to upgrade the methodology and the INDUSAC platform in the points described below.

III. LIST OF MONITORED PROJECTS

In the monitoring process for the first round of the Call for Students and Researchers, the Mentoring Committee selected 13 projects that started within the framework of INDUSAC and were completed in the end of May 2024. Within the second round, the Mentoring Committee selected 7 projects that were completed in the end of September 2024. Finally, in the third round of monitoring, corresponding to the fourth and fifth round of co-creation projects, the Mentoring Committee reviewed 10 projects that were completed mainly in January 2025. These projects are as follows:

Table 1 : List of monitored projects

Challenge	PCA	Co-creation team ID	Mentoring Committee members	
			Member #1	Member #2
First round, cut-off 11. 2. 2024				
Transitioning from a physical-type company to a digital one	7	414063	CUT: Eliza Nikolaou	CIT UPC: Radivoj Malić
Robot fleet manager from open-source software	6	447068	JSI: Matjaž Spreitzer	CIT UPC: Radivoj Malić
Removal of micropollutants from municipal wastewater	8	247090	CIT UPC: Radivoj Malić	CCIPB: Szabina Pazaurek
Age-friendly banking and fraud prevention	1	484098	BAX: Harry Dobbs	CUT: Eliza Nikolaou
Future approaches in organic skincare marketing initiatives	3	1800101	JSI: Matjaž Spreitzer	BAX: Maarten Buysse
Future approaches in organic skincare marketing initiatives	3	4090101	JSI: Matjaž Spreitzer	BAX: Harry Dobbs
ReSoil® Web Revamp: Greening The Future By Restoring Degraded Land Worldwide	4	443055	JSI: Matjaž Spreitzer	CCIPB: Szabina Pazaurek
Battery electric vehicles - product opportunities	6	330066	BAX: Maarten Buysse	CUT: Eliza Nikolaou
Recycling gazeq safety products - responsibility for all, for everything	9	356074	CCIPB: Szabina Pazaurek	CUT: Eliza Nikolaou
Recycling gazeq safety products - responsibility for all, for everything	9	366074	CCIPB: Szabina Pazaurek	CUT: Eliza Nikolaou
pla:Fi the innovative pillow, marketing campaign	3	402093	BAX: Harry Dobbs	CCIPB: Szabina Pazaurek
Fun and easy to use "financial competence training & knowledge service" for people 50+	8	5000105	CIT UPC: Radivoj Malić	JSI: Matjaž Spreitzer

Challenge	PCA	Co-creation team ID	Mentoring Committee members	
			Member #1	Member #2
Innovative diversification: broadening horizons in die casting toolmaking	6	4000119	JSI: Matjaž Spreitzer	CIT UPC: Radivoj Malić

Challenge	PCA	Co-creation team ID	Mentoring Committee members	
			Member #1	Member #2
Second round, cut-off 18. 6. 2024				
Inovative Custom Made Hardwood Floors	3	6990103	JSI: Matjaž Spreitzer	CIT UPC: Radivoj Malić
Product labelling of the future	1	8550143	CUT: Eliza Nikolaou	JSI: Matjaž Spreitzer
Sustainability Challenge: Reducing Waste In Abrasive Materials Production	6	4470140	CUT: Eliza Nikolaou	JSI: Matjaž Spreitzer
Redesign And Updating ENVIT's ReSoil® Website To Enhance Global Engagement And Accessibility	4	4430174	CCIPB: Szabina Pazaurek	CUT: Eliza Nikolaou
New Ideas To Natural Skincare Marketing Approaches	3	4090132	CIT UPC: Radivoj Malić	BAX: Harry Dobbs
New Ideas To Natural Skincare Marketing Approaches	3	1800132	CIT UPC: Radivoj Malić	BAX: Harry Dobbs
Smart Tools	8	7770139	BAX: Harry Dobbs	CCIPB: Szabina Pazaurek

Challenge	PCA	Co-creation team ID	Mentoring Committee members	
			Member #1	Member #2
Fourth round, cut-off 30. 10. 2024				
Defining and Performing Analytical Techniques for Assessing Fisetin Bioavailability and Absorption Efficiency in Enhanced Formulations	8	10420201	CIT UPC: Radivoj Malić	BAX: Harry Dobbs
Alveus kitchen sink: The centerpiece of your kitchen	3	4990191	CIT UPC: Radivoj Malić	BAX: Harry Dobbs

Challenge	PCA	Co-creation team ID	Mentoring Committee members	
			Member #1	Member #2
Defining and Performing Analytical Techniques for Assessing Fisetin Bioavailability and Absorption Efficiency in Enhanced Formulations	8	2230201	CCIPB: Szabina Pazaurek	CUT: Mariza Vryonides
Defining and Performing Analytical Techniques for Assessing Fisetin Bioavailability and Absorption Efficiency in Enhanced Formulations	8	10550201	CCIPB: Szabina Pazaurek	CUT: Mariza Vryonides
AI Assistants: Automating and Streamlining Engineering Processes	6	2730197	BAX: Harry Dobbs	CIT UPC: Radivoj Malić
Young People Live Sustainably	3	9510179	BAX: Harry Dobbs	CIT UPC: Radivoj Malić
Competitor Analysis of ClimateLaunchpad (EIT Climate-KIC)	2	9620176	CUT: Mariza Vryonides	JSI: Matjaž Spreitzer
Fifth round, cut-off 30. 11. 2024				
Office of the future: tech to wellbeing	6	10150164	CUT: Mariza Vryonides	JSI: Matjaž Spreitzer
New Strategies for Marketing Natural Skincare	3	11450202	JSI: Matjaž Spreitzer	CCIPB: Szabina Pazaurek
Autonomous Roof Structure for Drone Hub	8	11520209	JSI: Matjaž Spreitzer	CCIPB: Szabina Pazaurek

IV. PROPOSALS FOR INDUSAC PROCESSES, METHODOLOGY AND PLATFORM IMPROVEMENTS

The students' and the companies' general impression of the co-creation projects was very positive. Projects are an excellent opportunity for students, as during their implementation, they get a good insight into working with the industry and trying to solve a concrete challenge. Until now, the students mostly had no contact with the industrial environment. Due to their lack of experience, the instructions must be clear, especially regarding the deadlines they must meet. At the same time, these projects also give the industry a good insight into the students' way of thinking and enable them to get in contact with new generations who have different values towards work. Many students would also like to continue to cooperate with the companies from their co-creation projects in the future. Many teams had weekly meetings with the companies and worked in topic-related subgroups. Below are comments collected from students, researchers, and companies. Among the comments are also some operative questions like funding and timeline that were clarified immediately during the meeting / conversation with the teams.

- One company suggested adding additional non-professional parameters into the team matching process, such as determination, willingness, and adaptability. The company would check for these parameters using appropriate questionnaires. The need to improve the matching phase was pointed out by some students as well. Students had problems forming co-creation teams. Connecting via the Slack application did not seem optimal to them. It was difficult to find and create a team that would meet all the requirements - both from a technical point of view, as well as geographically. It was also difficult to keep track of all the past communication. For those who joined the group later, they also did not see past posts. Direct communication between the company, the team, and the mentor(s) via current channels (Slack, platform, social media) is underused and not very effective. INDUSAC understands the expressed issues. However, at this stage matchmaking process relies on existing communication tools with all positive and negative aspects.

- One co-creation team mentioned that a mentor or a supervisor from the academy, with appropriate scientific knowledge, could effectively contribute to the progress of the team's work. The mentor would be involved in the work as needed, mainly for its guidance. One company proposed to upgrade the methodology in such a way that it would be possible to upgrade the challenge during the implementation of the project with new content and/or new students, depending on the development of the work itself. The company also proposed to upgrade the platform in such a way that it would allow the company to co-

finance the project in the event that the group implements additional content. INDUSAC supports the idea, as it might improve the quality of solutions prepared by teams, but such supervision can only be integrated into the methodology of replicated “post-INDUSAC” mechanism.

- Students would like the deadline for submitting results to be longer. Since they have other obligations, they cannot focus solely on the project. Projects should be announced for periods when students do not have exams.

- Students would appreciate some help from INDUSAC regarding taxation, as well as more detailed guidance on fund distribution and eligibility conditions: Determining all possible costs, showing how costs are divided for groups of different sizes; the students were wondering if it is possible that the groups are not entitled to the full amount. They would appreciate precise, short, and useful explanations, including a step-by-step guide for taxation obligations in each EU Member States:

- https://european-union.europa.eu/priorities-and-actions/actions-topic/taxation_en,

- https://europa.eu/youreurope/citizens/work/taxes/income-taxes-abroad/index_en.htm.

- The platform's upgrade was suggested by students to include a videoconferencing system for meetings. Students had some technical problems with submitting motivation letters. Sending notifications about the acceptance of motivation letters to the co-creation team and the responsible INDUSAC mentor(s) would be beneficial. Students also mentioned that it would be good to have a better categorisation of challenges with more filters, which would allow challenges to be divided according to topics (e.g. engineering, marketing, business challenges, etc.).

- Some companies had difficulties in preparing a challenge. Related to challenges, students would appreciate more defined and structured goals, especially from a technical point of view. Students expressed that they would like to see an example of the anticipated result. However, on the other side some co-creation teams would like to have more flexibility during the implementation process. Since students have not worked in companies yet, they do not know what the technical solution to the challenge looks like and what methods should be used. With the progress of the INDUSAC project, the number of challenges has increased and can serve as examples for new companies to prepare their own examples.

The methodology and platform can be enhanced with additional features to improve the effectiveness of co-creation teams, increase team member engagement, and ensure successful collaborations. The recommendations are based on the feedback from co-

creation teams and companies, as well as insights from the Mentoring Committee and are listed below:

Methodology:

- integrate agile project management techniques to help implement the project on a co-creation team level, i.e., sprints, scrums, and regular meetings to ensure continuous progress and flexibility,
- enhanced communication protocols: establish regular bi-weekly check-in meetings on co-creation team level, mandatory for students and optional for the company to ensure alignment and provide timely feedback, as already proposed in all PCAs.

Platform:

- project management tools: since INDUSAC platform doesn't have the capacity, we recommend companies and co-creation teams to utilise platforms like Slack, Trello, Miro, or Jira to manage project tasks, timelines, and deliverables,
- shared knowledge base: since INDUSAC platform doesn't have the capacity, we recommend creating a centralised space for document sharing, ensuring all project-related materials are easily accessible (Google Drive, Microsoft Teams, Trello etc.),
- outcome reporting: develop reporting tools to easily generate reports on project outcomes, lessons learned, and areas for improvement.

V. CONCLUDING REMARKS

The general impression of the co-creation projects from both students and companies was very positive, and their input for improvements was highly insightful. INDUSAC projects are a great way for students to gain valuable insights into working in the industry and tackling real-world challenges. Until now, the students mostly had no contact with the industrial environment.

The observations of Mentoring Committee could be divided into different segments of remarks such as:

1. Comments related to subjective external factors that are not relevant for all the students and / or companies. Examples: exam period, holidays, summertime.

INDUSAC assures that the deadlines and the conditions are well defined, known well in advance and that participation is possible any time since October 2023.

2. Comments related to subjective internal factors of the co-creation teams and / or companies that are not relevant for all the students and / or companies. Examples: late start of work of the team, unresponsiveness of the team or the company.

INDUSAC assures that the conditions of participation are the same for all participants.

3. Comments related to INDUSAC guidelines that do not affect the INDUSAC methodology itself. Examples: taxation questions, one questionnaire for companies instead of two, To-Do guidelines for each PCA type.

INDUSAC rules for participation, including eligibility, budget, fund distribution, taxation, precise list of deliverables per each PCA, timeline of co-creation projects, are defined in the Call for companies, Call for students and researchers, additionally explained in INDUSAC FAQ document. Teams, together with a company get individual e-mails with instructions. Reminders are sent out before the deadlines. indusac@ijs.si e-mail is available for sending additional questions.

In addition to the existing protocols, the Mentoring Committee suggests WP3 partners that even greater attention is put on sending clear, precise and timely guidelines to co-creation teams and companies. The Mentoring Committee also suggests including a link to FAQ document in all e-mails that are sent to co-creation teams and companies since most questions received during the mentoring are already answered in the FAQ document.

4. Comments related to INDUSAC processes that do affect the methodology and / or the platform. Examples: adding additional non-professional parameters into the team matching process, improving the matchmaking, adding a mentor or a supervisor from the academy, platform including a videoconferencing system, integrating agile project management techniques, enhancing communication protocols, sharing knowledge base on the platform, reporting tools,

For those cases, the Mentoring Committee suggests WP1 (for the methodology) and WP2 (for the platform) to review the comments and decide whether they should be implemented within the INDUSAC or taken into consideration when preparing D4.6 Replication of the mechanism including a business plan for the joint venture business (upcoming deliverable).

VI. LIST OF REFERENCES

Spreitzer M., Pazaurek S. 2024a. Report on In-Depth Monitoring (M22); Deliverable D3.4 in Quick Challenge-driven, Human-centered Co-Creation mechanism for INDUSty-Academia Collaborations (Horizon Europe project No. 101070297).

Spreitzer M., Pazaurek S. 2024b. Report on In-Depth Monitoring (M27); Deliverable D3.4 in Quick Challenge-driven, Human-centered Co-Creation mechanism for INDUSty-Academia Collaborations (Horizon Europe project No. 101070297).

VII. TABLE OF CHANGES TO THE PREVIOUS VERSION

page 2-3	updated History of Changes
pages 4, 5, 8	Update of Summary, Abstract, and Introduction to include reporting on the third round of the co-creation projects.
pages 10-12	List of monitored projects expanded to include those from the third round of the Call for Students and Researchers
pages 13-15	Proposals for improvements updated to include INDUSAC's position towards some of the expressed proposals
page 18	Previous version of the deliverable added to the Reference List
pages 60-79	Within Annex 2, Monitoring Forms of the 3 rd round of monitoring are added

VIII. ANNEXES

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ANNEX 1 : Monitoring Form template

Company	
Title of Challenge	
Type of a challenge (1-9)	
Duration of project	
Team members	
Mentoring Committee member(s)	
Dates of meetings with companies / co-creation teams	
Short description of monitoring protocol (e.g. status was checked once a week; etc.)	

Progress monitoring (checkmarks indicate that the co-creation project is running as planned; deviations from the plan, and corresponding adjustments are listed in the Problems and Troubleshooting sections, respectively)	
Period*	
Clarity of instructions	
Adherence to deadlines	
Delivery of results	
Problems	
Troubleshooting	

*KO kick-off meeting, MS milestone(s), FM final meeting

Short monitoring summary (e.g. project progressed without problems / specific problems were encountered and mitigated / etc.	
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ANNEX 2 : Monitoring Forms

Challenges from the first round

Team ID 443055

Company	Envit
Title of Challenge	ReSoil® Web Revamp: Greening The Future By Restoring Degraded Land Worldwide
Type of a challenge (1-9)	4
Duration of project	27.3.-24.5.2024
Team members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Md Abdul Roshid • Mohammad Zeeshan • Elene Miminoshvili • Vineeta Taneja • Geeta Reemoh
Mentoring Committee member(s)	JSI: Matjaž Spreitzer CCIPB: Szabina Pazaurek
Dates of meetings with companies / co-creation teams	20 May 2024
Short description of monitoring protocol (eg. status was checked once a week; etc.)	Communication with students and the company was established via emails.

Progress monitoring	
Period*	FM
Clarity of instructions	Yes
Adherence to deadlines	Yes
Delivery of results	Yes

Problems	N/A
Troubleshooting	N/A

*KO kick-off meeting, MS milestone(s), FM final meeting

<p>Short monitoring summary (eg. project progressed without problems / specific problems were encountered and mitigated / etc.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Students would like the deadline for submitting results to be longer. Since they have other obligations, they cannot focus solely on the project. - The students had very positive experiences with the project and want to cooperate with the company in the future. They highlighted the company's good responsiveness. - The company also has positive experiences with the students, which added that the challenges also grow with their work. - Students would upgrade the platform to include a video conferencing system to conduct meetings.
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Team ID 447068

Company	Ubiquity Robotics
Title of Challenge	Robot fleet manager from open-source software
Type of a challenge (1-9)	6
Duration of project	27.3.-24.5.2024
Team members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Kawtar Dhaidah • Muhammad Hamza Daud • Moenes Benaissa • Ahmad Asaad • Ibrahim Shaglil
Mentoring Committee member(s)	JSI: Matjaž Spreitzer CIT UPC: Radivoj Malić
Dates of meetings with companies / co-creation teams	17 May 2024
Short description of monitoring protocol (eg. status was checked once a week; etc.)	Communication with students and the company was established via emails.

Progress monitoring	
Period*	FM
Clarity of instructions	Yes
Adherence to deadlines	Yes
Delivery of results	Yes
Problems	N/A
Troubleshooting	N/A

*KO kick-off meeting, MS milestone(s), FM final meeting

Short monitoring summary (eg. project progressed without problems / specific problems were encountered and mitigated / etc.

- The company has already carried out similar test projects in the past and has some experience in this field. The company set a difficult challenge, and the group tried hard to answer the open questions. During the project, the focus of the work changed slightly from hardware to software.
- The company saw a lot of determination in the group in the motivation letter. The company also pointed out that they would suggest adding additional evaluation elements into the team matching process, mainly non-professional parameters, such as, e.g., determination, willingness, working on new things, etc. The need to improve the matching phase was pointed out by students as well. The company is also ready to help in the preparation of appropriate questionnaires and continue with new challenges within INDUSAC.
- Students expressed that it would be good to have a better categorisation of challenges with more filters.
- The company suggested that a list of expected results (as in: some general examples of what results should look like) would benefit both the students and the company.
- Students would appreciate some help from INDUSAC regarding taxation, as well as more detailed guidance on fund distribution and eligibility conditions.

Team ID 1800101

Company	Asya Grafy Bio Institute
Title of Challenge	Future approaches in organic skincare marketing initiatives
Type of a challenge (1-9)	3
Duration of project	27.3.-26.5.2024
Team members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nina Furman • Marko Jovanović • Ana Kolinger
Mentoring Committee member(s)	JSI: Matjaž Spreitzer BAX: Maarten Buysse
Dates of meetings with companies / co-creation teams	14 May 2024
Short description of monitoring protocol (eg. status was checked once a week; etc.)	Communication with students and the company was established via emails.

Progress monitoring	
Period*	FM
Clarity of instructions	Yes
Adherence to deadlines	Yes
Delivery of results	Yes
Problems	N/A
Troubleshooting	N/A

*KO kick-off meeting, MS milestone(s), FM final meeting

Short monitoring summary (eg. project progressed without problems / specific problems were encountered and mitigated / etc.

- Students had no problems and were satisfied with the project. They had weekly meetings and worked in groups as part of the project.
- Students are concerned about income taxation and want clear instructions from INDUSAC regarding this. They don't want to do anything wrong.

Team ID 4000119

Company	Orodjarstvo Križaj
Title of Challenge	Innovative diversification: broadening horizons in die casting toolmaking
Type of a challenge (1-9)	6
Duration of project	27.3.-26.5.2024
Team members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ramin Mahmoudi • Idd Yunusu • Tanuj Namboodri • Moenes Benaissa • Wafae El Majdoub
Mentoring Committee member(s)	JSI: Matjaž Spreitzer CIT UPC: Radivoj Malić
Dates of meetings with companies / co-creation teams	27 May 2024
Short description of monitoring protocol (eg. status was checked once a week; etc.)	Communication with students and the company was established via emails.

Progress monitoring	
Period*	FM
Clarity of instructions	Yes
Adherence to deadlines	Yes
Delivery of results	Yes
Problems	The company's challenge was very complex. Special skills were expected from the students, and even the goal of the project itself was not entirely clear.

Troubleshooting	They corrected the challenge and work plan according to the preliminary results.
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*KO kick-off meeting, MS milestone(s), FM final meeting

<p>Short monitoring summary (eg. project progressed without problems / specific problems were encountered and mitigated / etc.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Projects should be announced for periods when students do not have exams. - Projects are an excellent opportunity for students, as during their implementation they get a good insight into working in the industry. Until now, the students mostly had no contact with the industrial environment. At the same time, these projects also give the industry a good insight into the students' way of thinking and enable them to meet new generations who have different values towards work. - The industrial partner was very satisfied with the team, especially with the leader and his communication skills. - The group mentioned that a mentor or a supervisor from the academy, with appropriate scientific knowledge, could effectively contribute to the progress of the team's work. The mentor would be involved in the work as needed, mainly for its guidance. - Students expressed that they would like more guidance on how they can spend project funds.
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Team ID 4090101

Company	Asya Grafy Bio Institute
Title of Challenge	Future approaches in organic skincare marketing initiatives
Type of a challenge (1-9)	3
Duration of project	27.3.-26.5.2024
Team members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mihailo Milićević • Jana Delač • Aleksander Breznikar
Mentoring Committee member(s)	JSI: Matjaž Spreitzer BAX: Harry Dobbs
Dates of meetings with companies / co-creation teams	9 May 2024
Short description of monitoring protocol (eg. status was checked once a week; etc.)	Communication with students and the company was established via emails.

Progress monitoring	
Period*	FM
Clarity of instructions	Yes
Adherence to deadlines	Yes
Delivery of results	Yes
Problems	N/A
Troubleshooting	N/A

*KO kick-off meeting, MS milestone(s), FM final meeting

Short monitoring summary (eg. project progressed without problems / specific problems were encountered and mitigated / etc.

- Students worry about what they must do when receiving the funds regarding taxation. They want precise, short, and useful explanations. The case was highlighted for Croatia and Serbia.
- The students are very satisfied with the project, as they are in contact with companies and trying to solve a concrete challenge. The company is also satisfied because, through the project, they are in contact with the students and their ideas.
- The wish was expressed by the company that students from private universities could also apply for the challenges.

Team ID 5000105

Company	Brygge GmbH
Title of Challenge	Fun and easy to use "financial competence training & knowledge service" for people 50+
Type of a challenge (1-9)	8
Duration of project	27.3.-24.5.2024
Team members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Matevž Gortnar • Antonija Karin • Bogdan Buzadizic
Mentoring Committee member(s)	JSI: Matjaž Spreitzer CIT UPC: Radivoj Malić
Dates of meetings with companies / co-creation teams	10 May 2024
Short description of monitoring protocol (eg. status was checked once a week; etc.)	Communication with students and the company was established via emails.

Progress monitoring	
Period*	FM
Clarity of instructions	Yes
Adherence to deadlines	Yes
Delivery of results	Yes
Problems	N/A
Troubleshooting	N/A

*KO kick-off meeting, MS milestone(s), FM final meeting

Short monitoring summary (eg. project progressed without problems / specific problems were encountered and mitigated / etc.

- The general impression of the project by the students and the company was very positive.
- The company had some difficulties preparing a challenge.
- Students had some technical problems with the submission of motivation letters.
- The students were a little confused because some of the challenges were very technical, while others, e.g., dealt with marketing. On that note, students would like some filters that they could use to preselect only certain types of challenges.
- Students would like more defined and structured goals, especially from a technical point of view.
- Students found the To-Do Lists less suitable for their use. Companies do not need To-Do Lists to organise work in projects.
- Students had problems forming co-creating teams. Connecting via the Slack application did not seem optimal to them.

The students pointed out that the project was their first contact with the industry sector. They were a bit unsure about the work in the project, as they did not know what was right and what was wrong. Due to their inexperience, the instructions must be clear, especially regarding the deadlines they must meet.

Team ID 330066

Company	Hidria Advancetec. BU
Title of Challenge	Battery electric vehicles - product opportunities
Type of a challenge (1-9)	6
Duration of project	27.3.-24.5.2024
Team members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nina Kovač • Md Mehedi Hasan • Anja Svajger • Sabi William Konsago • Tim Hrovat • Tanuj Namboodri
Mentoring Committee member(s)	CUT: Eliza Nikolaou BAX: Maarten Buysse
Dates of meetings with companies / co-creation teams	Communication with students and company implemented via emails. No meeting from both sides were preferred. Email sent to both company and team on 22/05/2024.
Short description of monitoring protocol (eg. status was checked once a week; etc.)	

Progress monitoring	
Period*	FM
Clarity of instructions	Yes
Adherence to deadlines	Yes
Delivery of results	Yes
Problems	Company was not responsive to Mentoring Committee's emails, but team provided their solution on time.
Troubleshooting	Company was not responsive to Mentoring Committee's emails. Mentoring Committee's

	members sent follow up emails without having a response.
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*KO kick-off meeting, MS milestone(s), FM final meeting

<p>Short monitoring summary (eg. project progressed without problems / specific problems were encountered and mitigated / etc.</p>	<p>Company was not responsive to Mentoring committee's emails, but team provided their solution on time. No meeting from both sides were preferred.</p>
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Team ID 414063

Company	C.P. Young & Active Traders LTD
Title of Challenge	Transitioning From A Physical-Type Company To A Digital One
Type of a challenge (1-9)	7
Duration of project	27.3.-24.5.2024
Team members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Manal Abbes • Parnian Kashani • Makhosi Khuzawyo • Ekomobong Okopido • Ahlam Boubekri • Nouredine Hfaiedh
Mentoring Committee member(s)	CIT UPC: Radivoj Malić CUT: Eliza Nikolaou
Dates of meetings with companies / co-creation teams	Communication between students were established via emails. In our last communication with them (10 May), the team leader was not responsive. In the company case, we were in touch through emails and phone calls (last communication on 29th of April).
Short description of monitoring protocol (eg. status was checked once a week; etc.)	

Progress monitoring	
Period*	MS
Clarity of instructions	Yes
Adherence to deadlines	Yes
Delivery of results	Team submitted their solution.
Problems	The issue of this collaboration was that the company was sold during the solution implementation and the new owners were

	nonresponsive. The team was concerned about how to proceed.
Troubleshooting	We encouraged the team to complete and submit their solution. In such cases the INDUSAC Evaluation Board steps in to review the Solution.

*KO kick-off meeting, MS milestone(s), FM final meeting

Short monitoring summary (eg. project progressed without problems / specific problems were encountered and mitigated / etc.	The problem in this case was that the company was sold during the timeframe that the team worked on providing its solution. We encouraged the team to continue working on their solution. As it is foreseen in INDUSAC protocols for such cases, the INDUSAC Evaluation Board has reviewed the developed solution that was delivered in a high quality and in time and was consequently approved.
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Team ID 484098

Company	Brygge GmbH
Title of Challenge	Age-friendly banking and fraud prevention
Type of a challenge (1-9)	1
Duration of project	27.3.-24.5.2024
Team members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Jakub Burek • Cotogoi Mihaela • Hasa Ovidiu Alexandru
Mentoring Committee member(s)	CUT: Eliza Nikolaou BAX: Harry Dobbs
Dates of meetings with companies / co-creation teams	E-mail sent to the company and team on 22/05/2024.
Short description of monitoring protocol (eg. status was checked once a week; etc.)	Communication with students and company implemented via emails.

Progress monitoring	
Period*	FM
Clarity of instructions	Yes
Adherence to deadlines	Yes
Delivery of results	Company rejected solution. As it is foreseen in INDUSAC protocols for such cases, the INDUSAC Evaluation Board has reviewed the solution once again and rejected it as well. The justification can be found in D3.5.
Problems	Company mentioned few challenges in their collaboration with the team such as: Teams had to deliver certain deliverables based on PCA requirements (e.g. a SWOT analysis) that the company did not need nor wanted them to

	invest time in. INDUSAC Mentoring Committee members explained to the company that each type of Challenge (1-9) has a predefined deliverables that guide the team and the company to the result.
Troubleshooting	Company did not need the team to prepare required deliverables based on PCA. INDUSAC Mentoring committee explained to company that required deliverables should be completed.

*KO kick-off meeting, MS milestone(s), FM final meeting

Short monitoring summary (eg. project progressed without problems / specific problems were encountered and mitigated / etc.	The company did not want all required deliverables according to PCA to be implemented.
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Team ID 247090

Company	Hidrofilt Ltd.
Title of Challenge	Removal of micropollutants from municipal wastewater
Type of a challenge (1-9)	8
Duration of project	27.3.-23.5.2024
Team members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Egzona Osmani • Nina Kovač • Ramin Mahmoudi • Selly Ayu Janetasari • Victor Kweku Ayertey
Mentoring Committee member(s)	Radivoj Malić (CIT UPC), Szabina Pazaurek (CCIPB)
Dates of meetings with companies / co-creation teams	2024.04.23. e-mail exchange with company 2024.05.16. e-mail to company 2024.05.08. e-mail to co-creation team
Short description of monitoring protocol (eg. status was checked once a week; etc.)	Communication with students and the company via emails.

Progress monitoring	
Period*	KO-FM
Clarity of instructions	Everything understood and discussed in detail via e-mail between the company and team.
Adherence to deadlines	Yes
Delivery of results	Yes
Problems	Organization of KO – difficult to find suitable date for everyone. Co-creation team required

	more detailed explanation about the expectations from the company.
Troubleshooting	Clarification about the expectation and the completion of the TO-DO List.

*KO kick-off meeting, MS milestone(s), FM final meeting

<p>Short monitoring summary (eg. project progressed without problems / specific problems were encountered and mitigated / etc.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Company needed some direction about the usage of the TO-DO List and their level of necessity whether they expect the co-creation team to complete all tasks of the TO-DO List and in what format is suitable for both parties. - The team found the timeframe for the development of the project too short but was able to finalize everything within the deadline.
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Team ID 356074

Company	Q.P. Ltd.
Title of Challenge	Recycling gazek safety products - responsibility for all, for everything
Type of a challenge (1-9)	9
Duration of project	27.3.-24.5.2024
Team members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ramin Mahmoudi • Eszter Borsodi • Matevž Gortnar
Mentoring Committee member(s)	Szabina Pazaurek (CCIPB), Eliza Nikolaou (CUT)
Dates of meetings with companies / co-creation teams	2024.04.10. KO company and co-creation team participated 2024.04.30. e-mail exchange with company and co-creation team 2024.05.14. e-mail exchange with company and co-creation team
Short description of monitoring protocol (eg. status was checked once a week; etc.)	Participation at KO, e-mail with company and co-creation team every 3 weeks.

Progress monitoring	
Period*	KO-FM
Clarity of instructions	Yes
Adherence to deadlines	<p>The team requested additional time for submission due to the late start, the company agreed, but the submission process didn't allow it.</p> <p>The testing of the products sent by the company were conducted fully on time.</p>

Delivery of results	The team uploaded their materials, but indicated via e-mail to the company they would need more time for the development of a full business strategy.
Problems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The implementation of the project was delayed due to finding suitable time to clarify the expectations of the company. - Co-creation team found the deadline too short for properly conduct the testing and develop a report. - Company found the timeframe to provide feedback on solutions too short.
Troubleshooting	The company waived the submission of persona template and empathy map-company established regular communication to follow the progress of the solution.

*KO kick-off meeting, MS milestone(s), FM final meeting

<p>Short monitoring summary (eg. project progressed without problems / specific problems were encountered and mitigated / etc.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - E-mail with company and co-creation team every 3 weeks. - The team told the company due to their exams and the delayed start of the work they won't be able to present the full business model for them on time, the testing of the products was conducted, and the initial findings were uploaded to the platform. - The company wasn't satisfied with the results, there were discussions on resubmitting a motivation letter to have the necessary time for the development of missing parts but the company after all decided not to proceed.
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Team ID 366074

Company	Q.P. Ltd.
Title of Challenge	Recycling gazek safety products - responsibility for all, for everything
Type of a challenge (1-9)	9
Duration of project	27.3.-23.5.2024
Team members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ana Teresa Sucgang • Brandon Joshua A. Gococo • Inga Werecka • Solmaz Hajjalilou
Mentoring Committee member(s)	Szabina Pazaurek (CCIPB), Eliza Nikolaou (CUT)
Dates of meetings with companies / co-creation teams	2024.04.10. KO company and co-creation team participated 2024.04.30. e-mail exchange with company and co-creation team 2024.05.13. e-mail exchange with company and co-creation team 2024.05.22. e-mail exchange with company and co-creation team
Short description of monitoring protocol (eg. status was checked once a week; etc.)	Participation at KO, e-mail with company and co-creation team every 3 weeks.

Progress monitoring	
Period*	KO-FM
Clarity of instructions	Company clarified their expectations.
Adherence to deadlines	Team submitted their finalized documents within deadline.
Delivery of results	Team deviated from PCA-corresponding deliverables based on their agreement of the

	company, didn't submit the SWOT analysis and a business canvas.
Problems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The implementation of the project was delayed due to finding suitable time to clarify the expectations of the company. - Company found the timeframe to provide feedback on solutions too short.
Troubleshooting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Company established regular communication to follow the progress of the solution. - The company waived the submission of persona template and empathy map. - Co-creation team focused on the preparation of the business model and covered the testing of the products superficially.

*KO kick-off meeting, MS milestone(s), FM final meeting

<p>Short monitoring summary (eg. project progressed without problems / specific problems were encountered and mitigated / etc.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - E-mail with company and co-creation team every 3 weeks. - The timeframe was short to develop a business model on the level the company expected. - The team collected relevant, usable information for the company's operation, but the company expected more.
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Team ID 402093

Company	Ham d.o.o.
Title of Challenge	pla:Fi the innovative pillow, marketing campaign
Type of a challenge (1-9)	3
Duration of project	28.3.-30.5.2024
Team members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Elena Orfanidou • Matevž Gortnar • Tanuj Namboodri • Tanja Luznar
Mentoring Committee member(s)	Harry Dobbs (BAX), Szabina Pazaurek (CCIPB)
Dates of meetings with companies / co-creation teams	2024.05.16. e-mail to co-creation team
Short description of monitoring protocol (eg. status was checked once a week; etc.)	Progress confirmation via e-mail.

Progress monitoring	
Period*	FM
Clarity of instructions	Yes, after instructions from company and mentors.
Adherence to deadlines	Yes
Delivery of results	Yes
Problems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Initially team was unmotivated. - Difficulty in communication with the team members.
Troubleshooting	- Clarification of company expectations was requested.

	- Detailed description in addition to PCA.
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*KO kick-off meeting, MS milestone(s), FM final meeting

Short monitoring summary (eg. project progressed without problems / specific problems were encountered and mitigated / etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- Co-creation team discussed any problem with the company.- Some questions were raised regarding the financial compensation and tax regulation, that was clarified.
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Challenges from the second round (cut off date for students and researchers: 18.6.2024)
Team ID 6990103

Company	ALPOD
Title of Challenge	Inovative Custom Made Hardwood Floors
Type of a challenge (1-9)	3
Duration of project	10.7.2024-4.9.2024
Team members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mateja Srblijinović • Črt Švajger • Kosta Jovanovic
Mentoring Committee member(s)	JSI: Matjaž Spreitzer CIT UPC: Radivoj Malić
Dates of meetings with companies / co-creation teams	28 August 2024
Short description of monitoring protocol (eg. status was checked once a week; etc.)	Communication with students and the company was established via emails.

Progress monitoring	
Period*	FM
Clarity of instructions	Yes
Adherence to deadlines	Yes
Delivery of results	Yes
Problems	N/A
Troubleshooting	N/A

*KO kick-off meeting, MS milestone(s), FM final meeting

Short monitoring summary (eg. project progressed without problems / specific problems were encountered and mitigated / etc.

- In the very beginning, students were a bit confused between INDUSAC (PCAs) and the company's instructions/guideline. It was solved in coordination with INDUSAC Mentoring team.
- The students had an overall positive experience with the project and expressed having no problems or issues resolving the challenge
- The company also showed overall satisfaction.

Team ID 8550143

Company	Etiketa d.d.
Title of Challenge	Product labelling of the future
Type of a challenge (1-9)	1
Duration of project	08-09-2024
Team members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alexander Delobel • Ana Arsovska • Tajda Hladnik
Mentoring Committee member(s)	CUT: Eliza Nikolaou, JSI: Matjaž Spreitzer
Dates of meetings with companies / co-creation teams	11 September 2024 18 September 2024
Short description of monitoring protocol (e.g. status was checked once a week; etc.)	Email was sent to company and team members on 11 September 2024. Follow up email to company was also sent on 18 September, 2024.

Progress monitoring (checkmarks indicate that the co-creation project is running as planned; deviations from the plan, and corresponding adjustments are listed in the Problems and Troubleshooting sections, respectively)	
Period*	MS, FM
Clarity of instructions	Yes
Adherence to deadlines	Yes
Delivery of results	Yes

Problems	No
Troubleshooting	No

*KO kick-off meeting, MS milestone(s), FM final meeting

<p>Short monitoring summary (e.g. project progressed without problems / specific problems were encountered and mitigated / etc.</p>	<p>The solution was delivered on time, and the process went smoothly.</p>
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Team ID 4470140

Company	Eurol
Title of Challenge	Sustainability Challenge: Reducing Waste In Abrasive Materials Production
Type of a challenge (1-9)	6
Duration of project	09-09-2024
Team members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aimen Tanougast • Muhammad Ahmad • Muhammad Hamza Daud • Wafae El majdoub • Idd Mohamed Yunusu
Mentoring Committee member(s)	CUT: Eliza Nikolaou JSI: Matjaž Spreitzer
Dates of meetings with companies / co-creation teams	11 September 2024 18 September 2024
Short description of monitoring protocol (e.g. status was checked once a week; etc.)	Email was sent to company and team members on 11 September 2024. Follow up email to company and co-creation team was also sent on 18 September 2024.

Progress monitoring (checkmarks indicate that the co-creation project is running as planned; deviations from the plan, and corresponding adjustments are listed in the Problems and Troubleshooting sections, respectively)	
Period*	MS, FM
Clarity of instructions	Yes

Adherence to deadlines	Yes
Delivery of results	Yes
Problems	No
Troubleshooting	No

*KO kick-off meeting, MS milestone(s), FM final meeting

<p>Short monitoring summary (e.g. project progressed without problems / specific problems were encountered and mitigated / etc.</p>	<p>According to the company, meetings were held regularly via Zoom between the company and the co-creation team. Two to three meetings were implemented. The company mentioned that they are very satisfied with their collaboration with the team.</p>
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Team ID 4430174

Company	Envit
Title of Challenge	Redesign And Updating ENVIT's ReSoil® Website To Enhance Global Engagement And Accessibility
Type of a challenge (1-9)	6
Duration of project	18.7.2024-13.9.2024
Team members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Zainab Fatima • Mohammad Zeeshan • Geeta Reemoh • Elene Miminoshvili • Md Abdul Roshid
Mentoring Committee member(s)	CUT: Eliza Nikolaou JSI: Matjaž Spreitzer
Dates of meetings with companies / co-creation teams	11 September 2024 18 September 2024
Short description of monitoring protocol (e.g. status was checked once a week; etc.)	Email was sent to company and team members on 11 September 2024. Follow up email to company and co-creation team was also sent on 18 September, 2024.

Progress monitoring (checkmarks indicate that the co-creation project is running as planned; deviations from the plan, and corresponding adjustments are listed in the Problems and Troubleshooting sections, respectively)	
Period*	MS, FM
Clarity of instructions	Yes

Adherence to deadlines	Yes
Delivery of results	No
Problems	Co-creation team's efforts as a group did not meet the required standards, resulting in the challenge being rejected.
Troubleshooting	After communicating with both parties, Mentoring Committee inform both parties that solution will be evaluate by INDUSAC Evaluation Board.

*KO kick-off meeting, MS milestone(s), FM final meeting

<p>Short monitoring summary (e.g. project progressed without problems / specific problems were encountered and mitigated / etc.</p>	<p>The company mentioned that the final outputs did not meet expectations. It also mentioned that some students started working on the solution in the last days. Students did not send any updates on their work until August.</p> <p>On the other side, the team mentioned that they lacked project management by the company.</p>
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Team ID 1800101
Team ID 4090132

Company	Asya Grafy Bio Institute
Title of Challenge	New Ideas To Natural Skincare Marketing Approaches
Type of a challenge (1-9)	3
Duration of project	Team ID 1800101 27.3.2024-22.5.2024 Team ID 4090132 25.7.2024-26.9.2024
Team members	<p>Team 1 (ID 4090132)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aleksander Breznikar • Jana Delač • Jelena Grujicic <p>Team 2 (ID 1800132)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gabriela Suša • Nina Furman • Sara Epet
Mentoring Committee member(s)	CIT: Radivoj Malic BAX: Harry Dobbs
Dates of meetings with companies / co-creation teams	10 September 2024
Short description of monitoring protocol (eg. status was checked once a week; etc.)	Communication with students and the company was established via emails.

Progress monitoring	
Period*	FM
Clarity of instructions	Yes
Adherence to deadlines	Yes
Delivery of results	Yes

Problems	N/A
Troubleshooting	N/A

*KO kick-off meeting, MS milestone(s), FM final meeting

<p>Short monitoring summary (eg. project progressed without problems / specific problems were encountered and mitigated / etc.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Two teams were accepted for this challenge, as the proposed solution differed significantly. - One team was more focused on technical solution, and the other team was more marketing oriented. - As the company representative was the same, common meetings were held for both teams, they worked alongside, as the solutions were complementary. - Impression from students: Overall very positive experience; by-weekly meetings were held with the company; students' feedback is that Instructions from INDUSAC were clear; the company was very responsive and helpful, providing guidelines and support; the communication was smooth. - Company representative was also very much satisfied with student teams and produced result. - At the time the meeting was held, already a lot of results were produced, and the deadlines were respected.
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Team ID 7770139

Company	Libela orodja
Title of Challenge	Smart Tools
Type of a challenge (1-9)	8
Duration of project	30.05.2024 – 08.07.2024
Team members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S. M. Ashik Abedin • Faisal Ahmed • Roy Mritika • Namboodri Tanuj • Yunusu Idd Mohamed
Mentoring Committee member(s)	BAX: Harry Dobbs CCIPB: Szabina Pazaurek
Dates of meetings with companies / co-creation teams	1 November 2024
Short description of monitoring protocol (eg. status was checked once a week; etc.)	Communication with students and the company was established via emails.

Progress monitoring	
Period*	FM
Clarity of instructions	Yes
Adherence to deadlines	Yes
Delivery of results	Yes
Problems	N/A
Troubleshooting	N/A

*KO kick-off meeting, MS milestone(s), FM final meeting

Short monitoring summary (eg. project progressed without problems / specific problems were encountered and mitigated / etc.

- Team members find the INDUSAC guidelines to be clear on every topic, commenting that the FAQ sections are particularly useful when further understanding is needed.
- At times, communication with the company was slightly delayed. While no reason was given for this, it was suggested that the deadline being worked towards should commence upon the first meeting or email confirmation with the company outlining that the work is starting.
- Company and team primarily communicated through email. As the INDUSAC platform lacks a notification alert system, it was commented that an email to make the team aware of an outstanding INDUSAC message would be advantageous.
- Furthermore, the team outlined that the INDUSAC team is helpful and understanding, making it easier to work on the challenges.

Challenges from the third round of monitoring
Team ID 10420201

Company	Asya Grafy Bio Institute d.o.o.
Title of Challenge	Defining and Performing Analytical Techniques for Assessing Fisetin Bioavailability and Absorption Efficiency in Enhanced Formulations
Type of a challenge (1-9)	8
Duration of project	13.11.2024 – 6.1.2025
Team members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lučka Kaligarič • Martina Mileva • Marija Ristovska • Vanja Angjelovikj • Marko Arsov
Mentoring Committee member(s)	CIT: Radivoj Malic BAX: Harry Dobbs
Dates of meetings with companies / co-creation teams	05.02.2025
Short description of monitoring protocol (eg. status was checked once a week; etc.)	Emails + monitoring/feedback meeting after the solution was submitted

Progress monitoring	
Period*	FM
Clarity of instructions	Yes
Adherence to deadlines	Yes
Delivery of results	Yes
Problems	N/A

Troubleshooting	N/A
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*KO kick-off meeting, MS milestone(s), FM final meeting

<p>Short monitoring summary (eg. project progressed without problems / specific problems were encountered and mitigated / etc.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The whole experience was positive. • Coordination team gave them good instructions. • They had slight challenge fitting the Motivation Letter in the template, but they finally managed. • The project instructions were clear, they met the company early on. • The company was great. Good and frequent meetings were organized (mostly weekly and/or biweekly, with clear deadlines and milestones. The meetings were held to discuss the progress. • They had only one small issue related to the platform, as they had to repeat the questionnaire (did not save). • The payment process was not so clear to the teams (e.g. this team was asked to provide bank account details, and they wondered why, as they provided it already before the start. • Overall, the experience was very positive, and the team is looking into participating again for another challenge.
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Team ID 4990191

Company	Alveus
Title of Challenge	Alveus kitchen sink: The centrepiece of your kitchen
Type of a challenge (1-9)	3
Duration of project	13.11.2024 – 31.1.2025
Team members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Antonija Karin • Marko Lui • Andrea Anna Milin
Mentoring Committee member(s)	CIT: Radivoj Malic BAX: Harry Dobbs
Dates of meetings with companies / co-creation teams	05.02.2025
Short description of monitoring protocol (eg. status was checked once a week; etc.)	Emails + monitoring/feedback meeting after the solution was submitted

Progress monitoring	
Period*	FM
Clarity of instructions	Yes
Adherence to deadlines	Yes
Delivery of results	Yes
Problems	N/A
Troubleshooting	N/A

*KO kick-off meeting, MS milestone(s), FM final meeting

Short monitoring summary (eg. project	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One team member was participating for the 3rd time, and she shared that this company was the most responsive
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progressed without problems / specific problems were encountered and mitigated / etc.

one (compared to previous co-creation processes she worked on).

- Excel timeline template was very useful
- Instructions were clear, they saw a lot of improvements in the methodology and processes from the INDUSAC team part, and the impact on the whole co-creation process (companies more responsive, instructions clearer, overall smoother co-creation process).
- They met with company on regular basis, to follow the process, as well as communicated by email (written feedback on the progress).
- There was a small misunderstanding about timeline (company didn't let the INDUSAC team know, but they managed at the end, and the deadline was extended).
- Overall, the whole team is very happy with the experience, and two members that participated for the 1st time plan to participate again.

Team ID 2230201

Company	Asya Grafy Bio Institute d.o.o.
Title of Challenge	Defining and Performing Analytical Techniques for Assessing Fisetin Bioavailability and Absorption Efficiency in Enhanced Formulations
Type of a challenge (1-9)	8
Duration of project	14.11.2024 – 11.1.2025
Team members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lučka Kaligarič • Martina Mileva • Marija Ristovska • Vanja Angjelovikj • Marko Arsov
Mentoring Committee member(s)	CCIPB: Szabina Pazaurek CUT: Sara Mariza Vryonides
Dates of meetings with companies / co-creation teams	2024.12.09., 2025.01.08.
Short description of monitoring protocol (e.g. status was checked once a week; etc.)	Introductory e-mail was sent at the beginning of the project and one check-in e-mail per month

Progress monitoring (checkmarks indicate that the co-creation project is running as planned; deviations from the plan, and corresponding adjustments are listed in the Problems and Troubleshooting sections, respectively)	
Period*	FM
Clarity of instructions	Well received, no additional questions regarding templates

Adherence to deadlines	Timeline and submission deadlines were met
Delivery of results	Solution accepted by company
Problems	N/A
Troubleshooting	N/A

*KO kick-off meeting, MS milestone(s), FM final meeting

<p>Short monitoring summary (e.g. project progressed without problems / specific problems were encountered and mitigated / etc.</p>	<p>Project implemented successfully, minor details about solutions were specified with the company.</p> <p>Through extensive research the team analysed how supporting ingredients influenced absorption rates, their findings provided valuable insights into the most effective formulation strategies, guiding the Institute in the development of next-generation skincare and nutraceutical products.</p>
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Team ID 10550201

Company	Asya Grafy Bio Institute d.o.o.
Title of Challenge	Defining and Performing Analytical Techniques for Assessing Fisetin Bioavailability and Absorption Efficiency in Enhanced Formulations
Type of a challenge (1-9)	8
Duration of project	8.11.2024 – 5.1.2025
Team members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Damjan Georgievski • Iva Edrovska • Kostadin Mitkov
Mentoring Committee member(s)	CCIPB: Szabina Pazaurek CUT: Sara Mariza Vryonides
Dates of meetings with companies / co-creation teams	2024.12.09., 2025.01.10.
Short description of monitoring protocol (e.g. status was checked once a week; etc.)	Introductory e-mail was sent at the beginning of the project and one check-in e-mail per month

Progress monitoring (checkmarks indicate that the co-creation project is running as planned; deviations from the plan, and corresponding adjustments are listed in the Problems and Troubleshooting sections, respectively)	
Period*	FM
Clarity of instructions	Well received, no additional questions regarding templates
Adherence to deadlines	Timeline and submission deadlines were met

Delivery of results	Solution accepted by company
Problems	N/A
Troubleshooting	N/A

*KO kick-off meeting, MS milestone(s), FM final meeting

<p>Short monitoring summary (e.g. project progressed without problems / specific problems were encountered and mitigated / etc.</p>	<p>Project implemented successfully.</p> <p>This team focused on the analytical chemistry and pharmacokinetics aspects of fisetin bioavailability. Their approach involved: reviewing existing research to identify the primary absorption challenges associated with fisetin, evaluating different formulation techniques that led to the development of a systematic framework for measuring fisetin absorption using advanced analytical methods.</p>
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Team ID 9510179

Company	Malsch TechnoValuation
Title of Challenge	Young people live sustainably
Type of a challenge (1-9)	3
Duration of project	17.11.2024 – 16.1.2025
Team members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mohamad Ali Hajazi • Pavel Aftimicuic • Piotr Mazur • Nasibakhon Rasulova
Mentoring Committee member(s)	CIT UPC: Radivoj Malić BAX: Harry Dobbs
Dates of meetings with companies / co-creation teams	04.02.2025
Short description of monitoring protocol	Emails + monitoring/feedback meeting after the solution was submitted

Progress monitoring	
Period*	FM
Clarity of instructions	Yes
Adherence to deadlines	Yes
Delivery of results	Yes
Problems	N/A
Troubleshooting	N/A

*KO kick-off meeting, MS milestone(s), FM final meeting

Short monitoring summary (eg. project progressed without problems / specific problems were encountered and mitigated / etc.

- Team is very satisfied with the whole co-creation process and is grateful for the opportunity to work on real-life challenge of a real company.
- Their feedback is that INDUSAC guidelines were clear, and they were very satisfied with the support of the INDUSAC team (they emailed when in doubt and always received support quickly and accurately).
- The team had meetings every week (or every second week) with company and the collaboration was smooth.
- The only challenge they faced during the challenge solving was the marketing aspects of the challenge, as the team was comprised mostly of engineers, but with the help of the company, they managed. If they were to do it again now, they would maybe include a marketing/business profile in the team as well.
- The team was happy with company, and they are still in touch with them, and are even considering the further collaboration.

Team ID 2730197

Company	Hidria Advancetec
Title of Challenge	AI Assistants: Automating and Streamlining Engineering Processes
Type of a challenge (1-9)	3
Duration of project	20.11.2024 – 11.1.2025
Team members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anja Svajger • Martin Georgievski • Stefanos Heikki Panagiotou • Tim Hrovat • Timotej Šuman
Mentoring Committee member(s)	CIT UPC: Radivoj Malić BAX: Harry Dobbs
Dates of meetings with companies / co-creation teams	04.02.2025
Short description of monitoring protocol	Emails + monitoring/feedback meeting after the solution was submitted

Progress monitoring	
Period*	FM
Clarity of instructions	Yes
Adherence to deadlines	Yes
Delivery of results	Yes
Problems	N/A
Troubleshooting	N/A

*KO kick-off meeting, MS milestone(s), FM final meeting

Short monitoring summary (eg. project progressed without problems / specific problems were encountered and mitigated / etc.

- The team found that the challenge was quite broadly defined. They had some challenges to define the idea in the beginning.
- After the team met with the company for the 1st time, things became clearer, the company gave them more instructions and ideas, and they could go ahead from there.
- Working during the holiday time was challenging, but they managed.
- For one of the members, it was the 3rd time participating in co-creation challenge, so she could guide the team better. She saw the improvements in the processes since her 1st participation (e.g. expectations from the company were much clearer this time, as they learned this should be defined in the beginning).
- Procedures were clear and smooth; they were happy with INDUSAC support.
- The solution was delivered on time. There was a technical error on the platform, so the team had problems with submitting solution - INDUSAC was informed on 12. 1. 2025, team submitted right after it was solved (16. 1. 2025)
- The team suggested the INDUSAC team could give a bit more instructions/training to companies, so they better understand the process before starting the work with the teams.
- Overall, the team found the experience very valuable, to be able to work for companies on real-life challenges.

Team ID 9620176

Company	EIT Climate-KIC
Title of Challenge	Competitor Analysis of ClimateLaunchpad (EIT Climate-KIC)
Type of a challenge (1-9)	2
Duration of project	2.12.2024 – 28.2.2025
Team members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Egzona Osmani • Maša Kralj • Md Mehedi Hasan
Mentoring Committee member(s)	CUT: Sara Mariza Vryonides JSI: Matjaž Spreitzer
Dates of meetings with companies / co-creation teams	24 January 2025
Short description of monitoring protocol (eg. status was checked once a week; etc.)	Communication with students and the company was established via emails and Zoom meeting.

Progress monitoring	
Period*	FM
Clarity of instructions	Yes
Adherence to deadlines	Yes
Delivery of results	Yes
Problems	N/A
Troubleshooting	N/A

*KO kick-off meeting, MS milestone(s), FM final meeting

Short monitoring summary (eg. project progressed without problems / specific problems were encountered and mitigated / etc.

The group said the instructions are clear, the platform is working well, the work is going smoothly, and they have no problems. Students understand their duties. The group wants more realized projects, as they are meaningful both for the students and for the company.

Team ID 10150164

Company	Trixin d.o.o.
Title of Challenge	Office of the future: tech to wellbeing
Type of a challenge (1-9)	6
Duration of project	2.12.2024 – 3.1.2025
Team members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Margarita Stafanowitch • Mariia Panasiuk • Masha Schneider • Valentyna Panasiuk
Mentoring Committee member(s)	CUT: Sara Mariza Vryonides JSI: Matjaž Spreitzer
Dates of meetings with companies / co-creation teams	27 January 2025
Short description of monitoring protocol (eg. status was checked once a week; etc.)	Communication with students and the company was established via emails and Zoom meeting.

Progress monitoring	
Period*	FM
Clarity of instructions	Yes
Adherence to deadlines	Yes
Delivery of results	Yes
Problems	N/A
Troubleshooting	N/A

*KO kick-off meeting, MS milestone(s), FM final meeting

Short monitoring summary (eg. project progressed without problems / specific problems were encountered and mitigated / etc.

The company representative announced that, in his opinion, the challenge preparation is too structured, the number of questions is too large, and the documentation contains too much text. He would like more flexibility in the whole process. The set deadlines seem too short for him. He had the feeling that the students were overusing artificial intelligence tools in their work. The members of the Mentoring committee explained to him the formal framework of the project and the limitations set by the financier.

Team ID 11450202

Company	ASYA GRAFY BIO INSITUTE d.o.o.
Title of Challenge	New Strategies for Marketing Natural Skincare
Type of a challenge (1-9)	3
Duration of project	12.12.2024 – 4.2.2025
Team members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dragan Jovanovski • Sabrina Jurkošek • Maša Ćorović
Mentoring Committee member(s)	JSI: Matjaž Spreitzer CCIPB: Szabina Pazaurek
Dates of meetings with companies / co-creation teams	28 January 2025
Short description of monitoring protocol (eg. status was checked once a week; etc.)	Communication with students and the company was established via emails and Zoom meeting.

Progress monitoring	
Period*	FM
Clarity of instructions	Yes
Adherence to deadlines	Yes
Delivery of results	Yes
Problems	N/A
Troubleshooting	N/A

*KO kick-off meeting, MS milestone(s), FM final meeting

Short monitoring summary (eg. project progressed without problems / specific problems were encountered and mitigated / etc.

The group meets weekly. The members of the project group are satisfied with the progress of the work. The company finds the projects meaningful, as the students bring a lot of fresh and bold ideas to the work of the company. In addition, the students are also satisfied, as they connect and get an insight into the operation of the company. At the beginning, the students did not know exactly what to expect from the project. The group has had no problems so far, and they have no suggestions for improvement. The representative of the company is of the opinion that the project could allow more flexibility in the implementation process, it would make sense that the company itself could determine the format of the reports, and the proposals would be non-binding.

Team ID 11520209

Company	Airbridge Global
Title of Challenge	Autonomous Roof Structure for Drone Hub
Type of a challenge (1-9)	8
Duration of project	15.12.2024 – 2.3.2025
Team members	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ajhan Skenderoski • João Pedro da Silva Moreira dos Santos • Slavica Dimkoska
Mentoring Committee member(s)	JSI: Matjaž Spreitzer CCIPB: Szabina Pazaurek
Dates of meetings with companies / co-creation teams	22 January 2025
Short description of monitoring protocol (eg. status was checked once a week; etc.)	Communication with students and the company was established via emails and Zoom meeting.

Progress monitoring	
Period*	FM
Clarity of instructions	Yes
Adherence to deadlines	Yes
Delivery of results	Yes
Problems	N/A
Troubleshooting	N/A

*KO kick-off meeting, MS milestone(s), FM final meeting

Short monitoring summary (eg. project progressed without problems / specific problems were encountered and mitigated / etc.

The company proposed to upgrade the methodology in such a way that it would be possible to upgrade the challenge during the implementation of the project with new content and/or new students, depending on the development of the work itself. The company also proposes to upgrade the platform in such a way that it would allow the company to co-finance the project in the event that the group implements additional content. The group would like more flexibility in the implementation of the project, as the dynamics of work can depend on the type of the project (this can be e.g. more engineering or more marketing oriented). Additionally, tight deadlines can also be problematic during the holidays. Everyone is otherwise very satisfied with the implementation of the project.

IX. LIST OF TABLES

Table 1 : List of monitored projects..... 10

